

8-*p*-Tolyl Sulphonamido-Quinoline as a Chelating Agent in Inorganic Analysis

R. C. AGARWAL

Department of Chemistry, D. Jain College, Baraut

Manuscript received 10 July 1974; accepted 9 October 1974.

8-*p*-Tolylsulphonamido quinoline has been used as a gravimetric reagent for Al (III), Zn(II) and Mg (II) at pH 4.5, 5.0 and 9.0 respectively. The Al-complex has 1:3 and Mg and Zn complexes 1:2-metal ligand composition.

8-HYDROXYQUINOLINE¹ had been used as analytical reagent since long. The reagent however lacks specificity and attempts had been made to modify the structure of oxine to improve its specificity. 2-Methyloxine^{2,3}, 2-phenyloxine⁴, 5-nitrosooxine⁴, 2-methyl-5-nitrosooxine⁵, 7-allyloxine⁶, 7-allyl-5-nitrosooxine⁶ are noteworthy. In the present communication we have examined 8-sulphonamido-quinolines as chelating agents since the sulphonamido (-NH.SO₂-) group being weakly acidic may coordinate through nitrogen with the replacement of hydrogen atom. We have found 8-*p*-tolylsulphonamidoquinoline to be an excellent chelating gravimetric reagent for Al(III), Mg(II) and Zn(II).

3. 8-*p*-Aminobenzenesulphonamidoquinoline (III);
R=NH₂

I and III were prepared by methods mentioned in literature^{7,8}, II was prepared by a similar procedure (m. p. 210°) Analysis (found: C=55.04, H=3.30, N=12.95, S=9.6; Cal. for C₁₅H₁₁O₄N₃S: C=54.47; H=3.35, N=12.76, S=9.9).

Experimental

The following sulphonamido-derivatives of 8-aminoquinoline were prepared:

1. 8-*p*-Tolylsulphonamidoquinoline (I); R=CH₃
2. 8-*p*-Nitrophenylsulphonamidoquinoline, (II);
R=NO₂

Reaction towards metal ions: Based on preliminary studies of the reagents I to III with different metal ions the results obtained with 8-*p*-tolylsulphonamidoquinoline (I) are recorded in Table 1. It could be seen that the reagent formed insoluble complexes with Al(III), Mg(II), Zn(II) and Cu(II) quantitatively at certain pH values. Estimation of Cu(II) was not pursued as there are much better reagents for it.

TABLE 1—REACTION OF 8-P-TOLYLSULPHONAMIDOQUINOLINE WITH METAL IONS

Ion	pH of initial precipitation	pH for complete precipitation	Colour of complex	Properties of the complex
Al(III)	2.0	4.0-9.5	pale-yellow	Granular, stable towards heat
Bi(III)	4.8	5.4-9.2	pale-yellow	Unstable towards heat
Ba(II)	7.0	8.0-11.0	pale-yellow	Fine ppt., fairly sol. in water
Be(II)	7.0	8.0	yellow	Granular, unstable towards heat
Ca(II)	7.0	8.5	pale-yellow	Fine ppt. slightly sol. in water
Cd(II)	5.0	5.5-11.5	pale-yellow	Fine ppt. slightly sol. in water
Co(II)	4.8	5.4-9.2	pink	Granular slightly sol. in water
Cu(II)	2.5	3.0-7.0	brown	Granular, stable towards heat
Fe(III)	2.4	4.0-11.0	bluish-black	Granular, unstable towards heat
Pb(II)	5.0	8.5	bright-yellow	Fine ppt. slightly sol. in water
Mg(II)	7.0	8.5	dirty-yellow	Granular, stable towards heat
Mn(II)	4.8	5.5-9.5	dirty-brown	Unstable towards heat
MoO ₄ ²⁻	2.5	4.5-8.5	Orange	Unstable towards heat
Ni(II)	4.8	5.5-10.5	Yellow	Granular, unstable towards heat
Ti(IV)	4.5	5.8-8.8	Orange	Unstable towards heat
Th(IV)	4.8	6.0-8.8	Yellow	Unstable towards heat
UO ₂ (II)	4.8	5.5-9.5	Yellow	Unstable towards heat
VO ₂ (I)	1.8	3.5-7.0	Green	Unstable towards heat
WO ₄ ²⁻	4.8	6.2-7.0	Green	Unstable towards heat
Zn(II)	3.3	3.3	dirty-yellow	Granular, stable towards heat

8-*p*-Nitrophenylsulphonamidoquinoline(II) and 8-*p*-aminobenzenesulphonamidoquinoline(III) are found to react with the metal ions in the pH range, more or less, the same as the reagent (I). The nitro-compound has the disadvantage of being insoluble in water and alcohol whereas (III) does not show any special advantage over the compound (I).

Gravimetric determination of Al(III), Mg(II) and Zn(II). Preparation of solutions: 1% Reagent solution in alcohol was used in all determinations. Standard Al(III) solution was prepared by dissolving A. R., B. D. H. potash alum in distilled water and its aluminium content was determined with oxine. Standard Mg(II) and Zn(II) solutions were prepared by dissolving A. R., B. D. H. magnesium sulphate and zinc sulphate respectively in distilled water and determining the metal content by pyrophosphate method. Other metal ion solutions were prepared by dissolving 1 g. of their A.R. quality salts in 100 g. distilled water for quantitative separations.

Determination of aluminium: A solution of potash alum containing 5-10 mg of Al, was diluted to about 80 ml. with distilled water. 2 ml. of 10% ammonium acetate were added to it and pH adjusted at 4.5 by adding *N*-acetic acid. It was heated to 60° and the reagent solution added dropwise with constant stirring till complete precipitation. The pale yellow complex of Al(III) was digested on a hot plate at 70°-75° for 30 min and allowed to settle down. Complete precipitation was again tested and the precipitate filtered through a glass-sintered crucible No. 3 and washed with hot water to remove SO₄ ions and the excess of the reagent. The precipitate was dried to a constant weight at 120°-125°.

Determination of Zinc: The procedure for the determination of Zn(II) was the same as that of Al(III) except that the pH was adjusted at 5.0 and the precipitate dried at 130°.

Determination of magnesium: A solution of magnesium sulphate containing 5-10 mg of the metal was diluted to about 100 ml. and A. R. ammonium chloride (2 g) and *O*-cresolphthalein indicator (0.2% in alcohol, 0.5 ml) were added to it, followed by 20% ammonium hydroxide till violet colour persisted (pH about 9.4). The solution was then heated to 75°-80° and the reagent solution added slowly with constant stirring, when a dirty yellow complex of Mg(II) got separated as a granular precipitate. The precipitate after testing for complete precipitation was digested at 60°-70° for 10 min and filtered through a sintered crucible no. 3, washed with 0.5% ammonia solution and dried at 125° to a constant weight.

Interference of other metal ions and their control: Be(II), Mg(II), Ba(II), Ca(II), Sr(II) and Pb(II) were found to precipitate out by the reagent only in the alkaline range, hence their presence as foreign ions did not create any interference in the estimation of Al(III) or Zn(II). Mn(II), Cd(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Ti(IV), Th(IV)

WO₄²⁻ and UO₄²⁻ did not offer any interference in the estimation of Al(III) and Zn(II) at pH 4.5 since they were not precipitated at this pH. In all the estimations in presence of these foreign metal ions results with less than ± 0.5% error were noted.

Results and Discussion

The pale yellow complex of Al(III) with the reagent(I) is soluble in chloroform, benzene and ether, moderately soluble in acetone and only slightly soluble in alcohol. It can be crystallised out from acetone in the form of fine pale-yellow needles m. p. 198°. The complex does not show any sign of decomposition below its m. p. and can be safely dried at 120°-125° to a constant weight in about 30 minutes. Analysis: (found C=63.40, H=4.35, N=9.18, S=10.30, Al=29.30; Calc. for (C₁₆H₁₃O₂N₂)₃ Al: C=62.73, H=4.28, N=9.15, S=10.44, Al=29.38%) shows the formation of (C₁₆H₁₃O₂N₂S)₃ Al complex. Mol. wt; found 905; Calc. for (C₁₆H₁₃O₂N₂S)₃ Al=918. This indicates that the aluminium complex is monomeric.

The zinc complex of the reagent is dirty yellow in colour, quite stable towards heat, insoluble in alcohol, partly soluble in acetone and readily soluble in benzene, chloroform, carbontetrachloride and ether. It is easily crystallised from acetone m.p. 184°. The complex is granular and can be dried at 130° without any decomposition. Analysis: found C=59.30, H=3.90, N=8.6, S=9.34, Zn=9.91; Calc. for (C₁₆H₁₃O₂N₂S)₂ Zn: C=58.27, H=3.95, N=8.5, S=9.71, Zn=9.92%. shows the formation of (C₁₆H₁₃O₂N₂S)₂ Zn complex. Mol. wt. found: 653; Calc. for (C₁₆H₁₃O₂N₂SZn)₂ 659. This indicates its monomeric nature.

The dirty yellow complex of Mg(II) is crystallised from acetone in the form of pale yellow needles m. p. 187°. The complex can be dried at 125° without any decomposition to a constant weight in about 30 min. Analysis. (Found: C=62.80, H=4.1, N=9.12, S=10.28, Mg=3.94; Calc. for (C₁₆H₁₃O₂N₂S)₂ Mg: C=62.14, H=4.20, N=9.06, S=10.35, Mg=3.93%) shows the formation of (C₁₆H₁₃O₂N₂S)₂ Mg complex. Mol. Wt. found: 605; Calc. for (C₁₆H₁₃O₂N₂S)₂ Mg, 618. This indicates that the complex is monomeric.

The reaction of the metal ions with the reagent can thus be represented as follows:

Conclusion: 8-*p*-Tolylsulphonamidoquinoline has been found to be an excellent reagent for the determination of Al(III), Zn(II) and Mg(II). It introduces a new series of organic compounds which possess good future prospects for inorganic analysis. The reagent is superior to oxine in the sense that the excess of the reagent can be easily washed out from the complex with hot water.

Acknowledgement

The author expresses his sincere thanks to Dr. R. R. Mehrotra, Principal, D. Jain College, Baraut for providing research facilities.

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